

Twin Transition for The Timber Industry

Deliverable 6.1

Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Plan

5G-TIMBER | Work Package 6, Task 6.1

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Table of Contents

1.	Executive Summary.....	9
2.	Introduction.....	10
2.1.	Mapping 5G-TIMBER Outputs.....	10
2.2.	Deliverable Overview and Report Structure.....	11
2.3.	Other project outputs.....	12
3.	Communication and Dissemination.....	14
3.1.	Why is Communication Important to 5G-TIMBER?.....	14
4.	Who will we need to communicate with?.....	16
4.1.	Engagement Strategy.....	16
5.	Tools & Channels for Communication and Dissemination.....	19
5.1.	Project's visual identity.....	19
5.2.	Website.....	20
5.3.	Social Media.....	21
5.4.	Communication and Dissemination Materials and Activities.....	23
5.5.	Events.....	27
5.6.	Timber Helix.....	28
6.	Dissemination and Communication Plan.....	30
7.	Exploitation.....	37
8.	Clustering Activities.....	40
9.	Management and monitoring of activities.....	43
9.1.	Partner's Responsibilities.....	43
9.2.	Monitoring.....	45
10.	Conclusion.....	46
11.	Appendix 1.....	48

List of Figures

Figure 1 5G-TIMBER logo	20
Figure 2 Project LinkedIn page.....	22
Figure 3 Snippet from the 5G-TIMBER 1st press release.....	25
Figure 4 Illustration of Crowdhelix recommender engine.....	29
Figure 5 Dissemination Tracker spreadsheet.....	44
Figure 6 5G-Timber brochure.....	48

List of Tables

Table 1 Adherence to 5G-TIMBER's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.....	10
Table 2 List of the other deliverables that produce inputs to this deliverable or consume outputs from this deliverable.	13
Table 3 5G-TIMBER target audiences	16
Table 4 Project target audience, key message and communication channels	17
Table 5 Social media channels and indicative target audiences	22
Table 6 Partner's indicative table of dissemination activities	30
Table 7 5G-TIMBER consortium initial exploitation intentions.....	37
Table 8 Related projects/initiatives.....	40
Table 9 Communication and dissemination KPIs.....	45

Glossary of terms and abbreviations

Abbreviation / Term	Description
5G	5 th Generation
DoA	Description of Action
GA	Grant Agreement
EU	European Union
DCCP	Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Plan
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
R&I	Research and Innovation

REA	Research Executive Agency
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
IWCMC	International Wireless Communications & Mobile Computing Conference
CIRP	Collège International pour la Recherche en Productique
WF-IoT	World Forum on Internet of Things
BEC	Baltic Electronics Conference
KPIs	Key performance indicators

1. Executive Summary

This report describes the work carried out under WP6 Task 6.1. Dissemination & Communication Activities (for Deliverable D.6.1 Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Plan). It outlines the following aspects:

1. the overall objectives of the project
2. the definition of the stakeholders and targeted audience
3. the communication channels through which a content-driven strategy is developed
4. the outreach activities to effectively reach the stakeholders
5. monitoring and evaluation procedures.

The report serves as the overall plan for the communication, dissemination and clustering of 5G-Timber. All project partners are expected to abide by the guidelines set out in this document and use it as a reference to execute their individual communication/dissemination plans.

2. Introduction

The Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Plan (DCCP) is designed for and in collaboration with the 5G-TIMBER partners. This deliverable will be an essential tool for the whole consortium, as each member will be involved in the communication and dissemination effort.

This deliverable lays out targets, responsibilities, processes and indicative timings for all these activities. It is designed to be a practical working reference for all consortium members when conducting their own communication and dissemination activities. This deliverable intends to be a working document which continues to be updated as the project progresses.

2.1. Mapping 5G-TIMBER Outputs

This section maps the components described in the 5G-TIMBER's Description of Action (DoA)/Grant Agreement (GA), i.e., the description of the deliverable and task description in the DoA/GA, against the chapters included in this deliverable and the justification of the work conducted in the project. See Table 1.

Table 1 Adherence to 5G-TIMBER's GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

5G-TIMBER GA Element	5G-TIMBER GA Element Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D6.1 Dissemination, Communication	Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Plan. This report will describe the dissemination and	Chapter 3-12	Dissemination, Communication and

and Clustering Plan	communication strategy, as well as engagement plan with other “sister” projects. it will also outline the dissemination materials including website development and social media accounts.		Clustering Plan for the project.
TASKS			
T6.1 Dissemination & Communication Activities	Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Plan (DCCP) outlines the project’s audiences, key messages, communication channels, roles and responsibilities and methods of communication to be used answering the questions (WHO? WHAT? WHEN? HOW?).	Chapter 3-12	DCCP for the project.

2.2. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The main objective of 5G-TIMBER DCCP is to disseminate the results of the research and development programme carried out by 5G-TIMBER, to communicate and disseminate its technological advancements and engage with the local, national and international communities from the outset of the project. The DCCP will provide a framework to promote the results, innovation and technologies developed to the appropriate audiences and to the society at large.

Through a strong communication and dissemination strategy, 5G-TIMBER’s overall objective is to:

- Communicate the project’s progress with the society
- Disseminate its achievements with the research community
- Engage with key communities

5G-TIMBER's communication and dissemination activities will:

- Implement a comprehensive **DCCP** ensuring a structured approach and concrete activities and tools
- Develop a project identity, website and social media presence, develop communication & dissemination materials and open communication channels to increase visibility, facilitate access to activities and results
- Increase awareness, build up knowledge and capacities in collaboration with defined target groups, including industry, SMEs and entrepreneurs, technology clusters, researchers and academics, policymakers, standardisation bodies, and the general public
- Facilitate national and international project synergies building on the network created by the Timber Helix.

2.3. Other project outputs

This section describes the interdependencies with the other project tasks and activities.

- a) Interdependencies between the task(s) of this deliverable and the other WPs:

Task 6.1 documented in this deliverable D6.1 is transversal to the project and thus provides background information, procedures, and guidelines to all the other WPs in terms of the project dissemination, communication and clustering activities.

- b) Interdependencies between the task(s) of this deliverable and the other –same– WP Tasks

Task 6.1 documented in this deliverable D6.1 is transversal to the project and overall WP. D6.1 will provide relevant inputs to Tasks T6.2, T6.3 and T6.4.

Table 2 provides a list of the other deliverables that produce inputs to this deliverable or consume outputs from this deliverable.

Table 2 List of the other deliverables that produce inputs to this deliverable or consume outputs from this deliverable.

5G-TIMBER GA Element	Contribution and Value of linkage
Output from D6.1 for D5.2 Initial Business Plan	D6.1 Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Plan outlines the partner's preliminary exploitation intentions for the project results. D5.2 will build upon that.
Output from D6.1 for D5.3 Final Business Plan	D6.1 Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Plan outlines the partner's preliminary exploitation intentions for the project results. D5.3 will build upon that.
Output from D6.1 for D5.4 Timber Helix set-up	D6.1 Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Plan outlines the objective and framework of the Timber Helix. D5.4 will build upon that and describe the process of creation and maintenance of the community.
Output from D6.1 for D6.2 Intermediate report on Dissemination, Communication and Clustering activities	D6.1 outlines the plan for the project's communication, dissemination and clustering activities. D6.2 will provide a mid-project report on those activities.
Output from D6.1 for D6.3 Final report on Dissemination, Communication and Clustering activities	D6.1 outlines the plan for the project's communication, dissemination and clustering activities. D6.3 will provide a project final report on those activities.

3. Communication and Dissemination

5G-TIMBER embraces best practices in terms of communication and dissemination as set out in various official EC documents.

Communication: Communication in projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results.

Dissemination: The public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.

Communication is therefore targeted at a broader audiences than dissemination, the latter being more suited to those who are interested in the outcome of the project as a potential user.

Communication and dissemination also translate into different objectives. When it comes to communication, the consortium is expected to approach society as a whole, and to make clear how the project will impact and benefit the general public. Dissemination, however, is characterised by an emphasis on knowledge transfer, and the technical application of the results.

3.1. Why is Communication Important to 5G-TIMBER?

An effective communication and dissemination plan supports outreach activities as well as exploitation pathways both during and after the project's

life. It is a key element in increasing the business outcomes from the project as well as its social awareness. This Communication and Dissemination Plan comprises a set of actions to explain and promote the project's achievements to the relevant audiences and to society at large. The diversity of the stakeholder groups will be addressed by tailoring the message and the communication activities.

The underpinning purposes of the communication and dissemination activities are:

- to raise awareness of 5G-TIMBER with target audiences and relevant stakeholders
- to enhance awareness about the project's results
- to support the use of 5G-TIMBER's achievements in the relevant contexts¹
- to avoid future duplication and encourage complementary research in the wood value chain, to increase the impact of EU funding by fostering research collaboration with sister projects and with all the relevant projects.

¹ <https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E.pdf>

4. Who will we need to communicate with?

In order to maximise the results of the outreach activities, they will be tailored for each specific group of stakeholders: 1. Industry, SMEs and entrepreneurs, 2. Researchers and related initiatives, 3. Policymakers and 4. General public. Establishing a strong affinity with the relevant stakeholders is fundamental, therefore generating important values of trust, care, and recognisability.

Table 3 5G-TIMBER target audiences

Target Audience	Description
Industry, SMEs and Entrepreneurs	Wood value chain manufacturers (e.g. wood, construction, biowaste); Manufacturing SMEs aiming to expand globally; Large industry planning to deliver customised goods and services at a local scale
Researchers and related initiatives	Universities, research centers, R&I departments of industry, related EU projects, European research organisations & alliances
Policymakers	National and European legislative and regulatory institutions; standardisation bodies
General Public	Citizens that might not have in-depth knowledge about manufacturing and technology but would be interested in having more acquaintances with them and understand the value of European Research.

4.1. Engagement Strategy

As a continuation of **Table 3**, where the target audiences were identified and described, we move forward on providing a specific engagement strategy

for each group, based on the needs and demands of each one of them, and the means of dissemination that we will use to achieve our objectives. Ensuring a dynamic interaction with the 5G-TIMBER targeted audiences is of utmost importance to ensure a long-term impact of the project outcomes, with the 5G-TIMBER consortium composition, allowing access to all the categories of audiences. Direct and indirect access through the partners' networks ensures that the dissemination and communications activities will be effective and will successfully achieve high reach and impact KPIs. A detailed description is provided in Table 4.

Table 4 Project target audience, key message and communication channels

Target Audience	Key message	Communication means	Strategic communication channels
Industry, SMEs and Entrepreneurs	5G-TIMBER contributes to small- and medium-scale manufacturing challenges in reaching green and sustainable development in terms of production efficiency increase, waste reduction and valorisation.	Direct participation in project initiatives, in person & online meetings as well as prominent industry workshops and associated industry interest groups; testing of operative tools such as toolkits	Timber helix events, and business/sectorial events
Researchers and related initiatives	5G-TIMBER opens research & innovation opportunities and transfer of knowledge about applications of 5G-enabled technologies in different manufacturing environments.	Research papers; publications; conferences/events; Direct participation in project initiatives; website, social media and press release	Academic publications, project conferences and events (e.g. Timber Helix events)
Policymakers	5G-TIMBER contributes to the decarbonisation of Europe by 2050 by	Direct involvement and policy	Policy recommendations;

	<p>improving the efficiency (materials, manufacturing, and logistics) of small/custom production by SMEs in the EU by 15% across different industries by means of data-driven collection and feedback of information.</p>	<p>workshops; operative tools such as toolkit, report and policy recommendations</p>	<p>conferences and project events</p>
<p>General Public</p>	<p>5G-TIMBER will contribute to meeting the growing demand for climate-friendly products and raw materials, enabling greater use of wood and wood-based products, and extending the lifecycle of wood to 100+ years to reduce waste and greenhouse gases.</p>	<p>Participation in project initiatives, social media channels</p>	<p>Website, social media and press releases</p>

5. Tools & Channels for Communication and Dissemination

To achieve the project objectives and support the dissemination and communication strategy, the following channels, tools and activities have been selected (where? how? and when?):

- Project's visual identity;
- Website;
- Social media;
- Communication and Dissemination Materials and activities:
 - Newsletters;
 - Press Releases;
 - Publications;
 - Brochures & Factsheets;
 - Project videos.
- Events
- Timber Helix

5.1. Project's visual identity

Project's visual identity has been developed as part of task T6.1. A brand manual has been created to detail how the brand should be presented in public and how consortium partners should come into contact with it. The brand created aims to provide a consistent visual identity of the 5G-TIMBER project. The brand will be used in the different materials produced under the framework of the project namely in templates, brochures, website, posters,

roll-up banners and videos. The brand manual is available to all partners in the Teams project repository and through this [link](#).

Figure 1 5G-TIMBER logo

5.2. Website

5G-TIMBER's website (<https://www.5g-timber.eu/>) will allow wide access to the project's main reports, news and public deliverables, and it will allow external stakeholders to get in touch with the project. The website was launched by M5 (October 2022) and will be constantly improved and updated throughout the duration of the project.

The website will also be regularly updated with news, events, relevant findings, achievements, and content extracted from the deliverables and reports. The website includes all the general information and updates about 5G-TIMBER, and is directed towards the general audience as well as target groups and stakeholders involved.

5.3. Social Media

5G-TIMBER aims to have a strong presence in social media, enhancing its outreach to target audiences and broad public and ensuring an active interaction with them. 5G-TIMBER's official social media pages have already been launched by M4 (September 2022). They include Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, ResearchGate and YouTube (see Table 5 for more details). The objective of these social media channels is to increase awareness and engagement within the targeted audiences. The social media channels will be updated on a weekly basis with posts concerning the project's latest updates, news, activities and events. Posts related to the project will when possible and relevant, mention some of the following accounts and hashtags in order to increase reach:

- Research Executive Agency: @REA_Research
- DG Research & Innovation: @EUScienceInnov
- European Health and Digital Executive Agency: @EU_HaDEA
- CORDIS: @CORDIS_EU
- #5G
- #AI
- #timber
- #manufacturing

Partners are encouraged to use their own social media pages to boost 5G-TIMBER's outreach by (re)sharing the project website and social media pages and its content, and by using 5G-TIMBER handles (@5gTimber).

Figure 2 Project LinkedIn page

Table 5 Social media channels and indicative target audiences

Social media channel	Link	Indicative Target Audience
Facebook	https://www.facebook.com/5gtimber	General Public
Twitter	https://twitter.com/5gTimber	Industry, SMEs and Entrepreneurs; Policymakers;

		Researchers and related initiatives
LinkedIn	https://www.linkedin.com/company/5g-timber	Industry, SMEs and Entrepreneurs; Policymakers; Researchers and related initiatives
ResearchGate	https://www.researchgate.net/project/5G-TIMBER	Policymakers; Researchers and related initiatives

5.4. Communication and Dissemination Materials and Activities

In order to communicate and disseminate the results, activities and project/related events effectively, the consortium – under the leadership of CHX – will produce and publish a set of visual and written content materials. They are an excellent way of systematically communicating relevant information about the project, such as objectives, past and upcoming activities, events, and updates on the project’s outcomes.

Newsletters

5G-TIMBER’s newsletters will include standard information about the project, including its name, list of partners, contact details, links to the project’s website and social media accounts and recognition of the EU funding. Each issue of the newsletter will be designed to reflect past activities and achievements, and to inform the readers about and promote future ones. Newsletters can thus include any recent publication of a deliverable or of a

paper, future events' dates and ways of registering, outcomes from consortium meetings, and any other updates.

5G-TIMBER's newsletter will be sent every 6 months to anyone who has subscribed to such updates from the project, would that be through the website, email enquiry, the Timber Helix or through personal contacts. To ensure the security of the stakeholders' data and to comply with the GDPR regulations, a dedicated mailing list for direct e-mails will be established and will be managed by CHX during its lifetime. In order to ensure easy access and consultation, all issues of the newsletter will also be available on the project's website.

Press Releases

The 5G-TIMBER press releases will be prepared in collaboration with the consortium partners and will include information such as: a non-technical summary of the project, partners' background and role in the project, information of specific milestones or deliverables, and other similar information. All press releases will include the 5G-TIMBER logo and will acknowledge EU funding. A first press release has been drafted and shared with relevant stakeholders after the project kick-off meeting (M1), see Figure 3. Further press releases will be drafted in collaboration with the consortium partners when needed.

Figure 3 Snippet from the 5G-TIMBER 1st press release

Publications

Partners will be encouraged to prepare and publish in open-access journals and articles. When writing scientific articles for conferences, journals and magazines, it is important to acknowledge the EU Commission funding by stating the following: *“This research is part of the 5G-TIMBER project, which was funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the Grant Agreement 10105850.”*; and also to clearly display the EU emblem so that it is visible to the public² (for presentations at conferences and other events, deliverables, posters, leaflets, and other communication materials, etc.). Moreover, partners should indicate that the publication reflects only the author's view and that the Agency is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. All research publications, including public deliverables and public parts of underlying datasets, will be uploaded to Zenodo European Commission-funded research (OpenAIRE) community. Zenodo is a comprehensive open

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/eu-emblem-rules_en.pdf

research data repository that collects research data from all disciplines. Open Research Europe allows researchers to publish any research they want to share, supporting reproducibility, transparency and impact. It uses an open research publication model: publication within days of submission followed by open professional peer review and includes citations to all supporting data and materials, allowing for reanalysis, reproduction, and reuse. D7.7 – Data and Ethics Management Plan further details the project process for publications in the framework of 5G-TIMBER.

Brochures and Factsheets

Brochures will convey simple and straightforward information, in order to engage with relevant stakeholders, and the society as a whole. While the visuals will be applied to all types of brochures, the text will be adapted to the target audience: technical, general, and potentially a different audience where needed.

The brochures will be prepared by CHX in collaboration with the project partners and will be made available to the consortium in the Teams repository (1st version available, please see appendix 1). The consortium will therefore be able to disseminate the project easily, providing gatherings and travel restrictions are eased within the coming months. 5G-TIMBER will also produce a set of different factsheets to boost the promotion of the project's results and outcomes. These materials will be available online in the project communication channels and distributed at different events.

Project videos

Dissemination videos will be prepared by CHX. At least two videos will be created 1) M12 – general information about the project and 2) M36 – key project results. The videos will be published on the project’s YouTube channel, the project website and social media as a way to raise awareness about the project, inform about outcomes and engage stakeholders.

5.5. Events

5G-timber partners will participate in national and international level conferences and events in order to raise awareness about the project’s activities and results, and foster uptake of its solutions. Partners will focus on promoting 5G-timber in key Industrial Exhibitions, Business Conferences and Trade Fairs which attract a high number of players across the sectors of interest, aiming to maximise the effect of direct interaction with relevant stakeholders.

A calendar of events (M10) will be created to organise and manage partners’ participation in different events in order to increase the outreach of the project. Indicatively, the consortium will be looking to attend the following events: IEEE GLOBECOM, IEEE International Conference on Communications, IEEE 5G Summit, IWCMC, IEEE World Forum on Internet of Things, Annual Meeting of the Northern European Network for Wood Science and Engineering, CIRP Annals, etc. To adopt the results in technology transfer and new R&I initiatives within industry, a final dissemination conference with at least 50 participants will be organised.

5.6. Timber Helix

A virtual community called the Timber Helix will be created and populated with consortium members, with a target of more than 150 organisations being members of the Helix by M36. This community will include relevant stakeholders creating a self-sustainable ecosystem for the project.

The Helix will be used as a main dissemination tool. Through this virtual Helix community, the project's stakeholders will be made aware of 5G-TIMBER's research outputs. The Timber Helix will continue to exist even after the project has finished as a self-sustained community, focused on facilitating collaborative partnerships. A Helix Manager (CHX) will be responsible for onboarding new members, connect the various stakeholders involved and maintain the community active and featuring various opportunities for collaboration. The Helix Leadership will be taken over by Innovawood. Innovawood will help to steer the community by assisting CHX in understanding the thematic landscape, connecting with relevant stakeholders and initiatives and providing support in the organisation of events.

A unique feature of the Crowdhelix platform is its matchmaking algorithm (recommender engine, see Figure 4) that adds value to both the Helixes and the organisations registered. This tool connects the posted opportunities with researchers and institutions possessing the required expertise or infrastructure. Once an organisation or an individual researcher registers for the Timber Helix and profiles their expertise, the platform's recommender engine will help the Crowdhelix team flag their expertise to suitable, available

opportunities within the Helix. The matchmaking algorithm can also be used to connect with various stakeholders and will be used to find specific collaborators for the project's future needs.

Figure 4 Illustration of Crowdhelix recommender engine

In order to draw on and steer this virtual ecosystem, CHX will organise 3 events (one per year) to bring the profiled organisations together and discuss topics of interest to both the Helix community and 5G-TIMBER. By the end of the project, CHX will organize a final project conference with at least 50 industry participants (by M36), aligned with the Helix event to exploit the project results.

6. Dissemination and Communication Plan

Table 6 specifies the dissemination and communication plans for each project partner during the project implementation.

Table 6 Partner's indicative table of dissemination activities

Partner Name	Year	Planned Dissemination Activities
TalTech	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Publish 2 to 3 papers in a journal (e.g. IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Access, etc.) ▪ Publish 1 or 2 conference papers and/or participate in e.g. IWCMC, IEEE WF-IoT, etc. ▪ Organize a discussion panel in the BEC2022 conference ▪ Post/share/reshare project news in social media, TalTech website, Estonian research information portal, etc. ▪ Participate in relevant events, e.g. Innovawood General Assembly Meeting
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Publish 1 to 2 papers in a journal (e.g. IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Access, etc.) ▪ Publish 2 or 3 conference papers and/or participate in e.g. IWCMC, IEEE WF-IoT, etc. ▪ Participate in project hackathon ▪ Post/share/reshare project news in social media, TalTech website, Estonian research information portal, etc. ▪ Participate in relevant events
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Publish 1 to 2 papers in a journal (e.g. IEEE Internet of Things Journal, IEEE Access, etc.) ▪ Publish 1 or 2 conference papers and/or participate in e.g. IWCMC, IEEE WF-IoT, etc. ▪ Participate in Helix Event ▪ Organise a tutorial or workshop or panel in BEC2024 conference ▪ Post/share/reshare project news in social media, TalTech website, Estonian research information portal, etc. ▪ Participate in relevant events
Inlecom	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Contributions to social media post, photos and images ▪ Support on press releases

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Meeting Images
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contributions to social media post, photos and images Support on press releases IP Workshop images Meeting Images
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Contributions to social media post, photos and images Support on press releases Patent Promotions Meeting Images
Athonet	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisation of UPTIME 2023 - The Private 5G World Community Conference, dedicated to Private 5G and LTE professionals Participation in the Mobile World Congress 2023 or other fair/trade shows to advertise the project 1 seminar for master and PhD students 1-2 joint journal or conference publications with project partners Posts on social media (Twitter, LinkedIn) to promote the project's activities
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisation of UPTIME 2024 - The Private 5G World Community Conference, dedicated to Private 5G and LTE professionals Participation in the Mobile World Congress 2024 or other fair/trade shows where to advertise the project 1 seminar for master and PhD students 1-2 joint journal or conference publications with project partners Posts on social media (Twitter, LinkedIn) to promote the project's activities
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organisation of UPTIME 2025 - The Private 5G World Community Conference, dedicated to Private 5G and LTE professionals Participation in the Mobile World Congress 2025 or other fair/trade shows where to advertise the project 1 seminar for master and PhD students 1-2 joint journal or conference publications with project partners Posts on social media (Twitter, LinkedIn) to promote the project's activities
Jotne	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Initial press release Statement about project start (LinkedIn)

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Internal newsletter status updates ▪ Reach out to stakeholders via industry association events, conferences, and standardization meetings, such as <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Conference – Spaceport Norway (25-26 Oct 2022) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Space expo held in association with the Norwegian space agency in Oslo, aimed at industry and academia. Jotne had an exhibition showing of our ESA, and Horizon projects ○ Conference – Industry Space Days - (28-29 Sep 2022) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Industry days and seminar held by ESA ESTEC aimed at industry to foster cooperation between different actors in the entire space sector. Jotne had a presence at the event. ○ Seminar- FSI Supplier seminar – (31 Aug -01 Sep) ○ Conference- Sensor Decade (1-2 Jun 2022) ○ ISO/TC 184/SC 4 meeting (31 Oct – 1 Nov) ○ Space Tech 2022 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Space trade fair ○ EF ECS 2022 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ European forum for electronic components and systems. ▪ Arrowhead Commercial Ecosystem
Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Milestone focused press release • Social media posts at significant milestones • Planned seminars on digital twins – drawing parallels to 5G-Timber • Participation in space, defence, and sensor related EU conferences • Internal newsletter status updates • Cooperation with academia such as UiO and NTNU (Trondheim and Gjøvik) • Cooperation in industrial networks for dissemination <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Norwegian Defence and Security Industry Directory (FSI), http://www.fsi.no/eng/ ○ Energy Valley (a technology cluster delivering world leading engineering from subsea to space), https://energyvalley.no/ ○ ProSTEP (digitalization partner for the manufacturing industry), http://www.prostep.org/en/

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ PDES Inc (consortium committed to accelerating the development and implementation of standards), https://www.pdesinc.org/ ○ The International Council on Systems Engineering (IncoSE), http://www.incose.org/ ○ Standards Norway (the Norwegian standardization body), https://www.standard.no/en/ ○ NAFEMS – International Association Engineering Modelling, https://www.nafems.org ▪ CENSSS – Centre for Space Sensors and Systems, https://www.mn.uio.no/censss/english/index.html
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Press release on project completion ▪ Posts related to significant milestones ▪ Workshop(s) on digital twins – drawing parallels to 5G-TIMBER ▪ Internal newsletter status updates ▪ Participation in space, defence, and sensor related EU conferences ▪ Cooperation with academia such as UiO and NTNU (Trondheim and Gjøvik)
Harmet	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Building Green Copenhagen https://buildinggreen.eu/cph/ Nov 02-03.22
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Bygg Reis Deg https://byggreisdeg.no Oct 18-21.2023
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Nordbygg www.nordbygg.se apr 23-26.2024
VTT	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Forum Wood Building Nordic, September 28-30, 2022, Aalto University, Espoo, Finland, Abstract accepted for oral presentation: Stefania Fortino, Petr Hradil, Timo Avikainen, Keijo Koski, Ludovic Fülöp. Hygro-thermal modeling of timber bridge decks considering the effect of solar radiation ▪ Press release of the project kick-off ▪ 1 LinkedIn post on “Teollinen Internet – Industrial internet in Finland” group with ~5k followers ▪ 1 LinkedIn post at VTT’s LinkedIn ▪ 1 Facebook post at VTT’s Facebook ▪ 1 VTT’s blog post
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ World Conference of Timber Engineering 2023 (WCTE2023), June 19-22, 2023, Oslo, Norway, 2 abstracts submitted for oral presentation:

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Stefania Fortino, Petr Hradil, Timo Avikainen, Keijo Koski, Ludovic Fülöp. A multi-phase hygro-thermal model for wooden bridge components exposed to solar radiation. ▪ Petr Hradil, Stefania Fortino. Integrated approach to predict deterioration of mechanical properties of decaying wood. ▪ +1 Conference paper ▪ 1 Press release ▪ 1 LinkedIn post on “Teollinen Internet - Industrial internet in Finland” group ▪ 1 LinkedIn post on VTT’s LinkedIn ▪ 1 Facebook post on VTT’s Facebook ▪ 1 VTT’s blog post
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 2-3 Journal articles ▪ 1-2 Conference paper ▪ 1 Press release ▪ 1 LinkedIn post on “Teollinen Internet - Industrial internet in Finland” group ▪ 1 LinkedIn post on VTT’s LinkedIn ▪ 1 Facebook post on VTT’s Facebook ▪ 1 VTT’s blog post
POLIMI	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Meccanica Magazine (magazine of the department of mechanical engineering at Politecnico di Milano). ▪ 2-3 Posts on the social media reported below ▪ Communication and dissemination activities within the CIRP community (https://www.cirp.net) through participation in meetings and sponsored conferences. ▪ Communication activities within the AITEM (Italian Association of Manufacturing Engineers) community.
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 2 papers published in International Conference Proceedings ▪ Potential demonstration at the Festival dell’Ingegneria ▪ 2-3 Posts on the social media reported below ▪ Meccanica Magazine (magazine of the department of mechanical engineering at Politecnico di Milano). ▪ Communication and dissemination activities within the CIRP community (https://www.cirp.net) through participation in meetings and sponsored conferences. ▪ 1 paper and/or communication activities within the AITEM (Italian Association of Manufacturing Engineers) community.
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Organize 5G-TIMBER Hackathon ▪ 2 Papers in International, peer-reviewed, scientific Journal ▪ 2-3 Posts on the social media reported below ▪ Meccanica Magazine (magazine of the department of mechanical engineering at Politecnico di Milano).

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Communication and dissemination activities within the CIRP community (https://www.cirp.net) through participation in meetings and sponsored conferences. Communication activities within the AITEM (Italian Association of Manufacturing Engineers) community.
Innovawood	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No specific plans for this partner at the submission date of this report. The partner will contribute to the overall dissemination and communication of the project. Timber Helix Leadership: communicate the project and this virtual community to possible members Co-organize Helix events
	Y2	
	Y3	
Hekotek	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No specific plans for this partner at the submission date of this report. The partner will contribute to the overall dissemination and communication of the project.
	Y2	
	Y3	
Tieto (FI & SE)	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Created https://www.researchgate.net/project/5G-TIMBER on Researchgate to update the scientific community.
	Y2	
	Y3	
Octavic	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press release- already done Social media post Link on website
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press release Social media post
	Y3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Press release Social media post
Thales (FR & DE)	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> No specific plans for this partner at the submission date of this report. The partner will contribute to the overall dissemination and communication of the project. Thales DE: Ongoing acquisition deal with Telit. Information cannot be shared now due to anti-trust regulations.
	Y2	
	Y3	
ACC	Y1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regular updates on social media channels Conference and Trade Fair attendance (MWC, EuCNC. Open RAN Summit, TIP Summit, ...) Possible joint dissemination activities with project 5G partners (e.g. Athonet, Thalys - https://5gconsortium.com/) Internal project dissemination activities Press Releases Trade Press Interviews
	Y2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regular updates on social media channels

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Conference and Trade Fair attendance (MWC, EuCNC. Open RAN Summit, TIP Summit, ...) ▪ Possible joint dissemination activities with project 5G partners (e.g. Athonet, Thalys - https://5gconsortium.com/) ▪ Dissemination activities at the company level ▪ Press Releases ▪ Trade Press Interviews
<p>Y3</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Regular updates on social media channels ▪ Conference and Trade Fair attendance (MWC, EuCNC. Open RAN Summit, TIP Summit, ...) ▪ Possible joint dissemination activities with project 5G partners (e.g. Athonet, Thalys - https://5gconsortium.com/) ▪ Internal project dissemination activities ▪ Press Releases ▪ Trade Press Interviews ▪ Possible whitepaper on deploying 5G Open-RAN in SMEs ▪ Possible whitepaper on Zero-Touch 5G Open-RAN deployments

7. Exploitation

Exploitation is the use of the results during and after the project's implementation. It can be for commercial purposes but also for improving policies, and for tackling economic and societal problems. Exploitation in 5G-TIMBER will be rooted on synergies between WP5 - Commercialisation, innovation management and standardisation and WP6 - Dissemination, communication and scale-up. As the work is WP5 in still in its inception, we will list the partner's exploitation intentions (See Table 7) in order to align early on the activities of both WPs. We will ensure strong and close collaboration between the WP and task leaders in WP5 and WP6, particularly ICP and CHX in order to maximise the impact of the project results.

Table 7 5G-TIMBER consortium initial exploitation intentions

Partner	Initial Exploitation Intentions
Harmet	Production efficiency improvement for the cost reduction: use of data driven product design and production methods, software components for non-conformances reduction construction sites; • will use DT assisted assembly in whole modules production process • will use AR and DT technologies in training and safety procedures. Will be able to rely more on external construction companies for the renovation projects. Will expect additional income from the temporary houses market; will be able to increase yield of modules reuse.
Jotne	Jotne will incorporate the project's enhancements in DT technology into their products & disseminate through marketing channels to existing companies & networks like AIA/ASD, FSI, NIFRO, PDES, SME4Space, EnergyValley and similar.
POLIMI	POLIMI will assist the software providers (Tieto FI & SWE) in validating the proposed approaches and identifying the most promising features supporting the future commercialisation• will benefit from the possibility to acquire a deeper knowledge of the WVC and support future R&I in this area.

Hekotek	HEKOTEK will reduce the amount of machine design errors via operational data analysis (including automatic machine vision), will increase assembly productivity using AR and DTs, will enable predictive maintenance for new and existing installation (incl. South-America, Siberia). Will reduce machine servicing costs (>15%), reduce machines downtime (>10%), increase machines operational efficiency during night shifts and decrease service costs of clients, additional income from spare parts predictive sales.
Athonet	Athonet will exploit the knowledge and expertise acquired during the project to develop innovative commercial solutions for the timber vertical, to strengthen its position as a 5G provider on the market.
VTT	VTT will improve its wood material models (DigiMoist etc.) and will use the input and outputs of the related FEM analyses for wood performance within the VTT Modelling Factory interface to provide a common backend and database system for lifecycle data processing in connection with LCA softwares (TRL 4 to 7);• will directly feed into the future exploitation of material model development for industrial use that forms the core of VTT activities.• VTT's O&M tools will be exploited for predictive maintenance within IoT services in timber processing environments for decision making and RUL assessment.
Thales	THA DIS&AIS will commercialise and sell the security solution developed during 5G-TIMBER project to customers for industrial environments, benefitting by strengthening its position in the market of secure by design industrial solutions.
ICP	ICP will develop new business models based on the outputs of the project, which will result in attracting new companies into its customer base, as well as assist in disseminating the developed business models, with their innovation and sustainability components, to a larger pool of companies.
CHX & IW	CHX&IW will disseminate project results through the Helix platform and Innovawood network, promoting innovative & sustainable data-driven solutions in wood manufacturing & production, contributing to CO ² neutral production of wood products beyond the lifetime of the project.
Tieto	TietoSE&FI will be able to identify the unmet needs of their customers in WVC and utilize XR technology and new communication protocols to find new solutions. As part of the consortium, TIETO can connect the data, machinery equipment, XR hardware and human operators in a single experience and service framework, consisting of modules that apply to multiple industries and customer segments.
ACC	ACC will improve its commercially available RAN solutions with innovations developed in the project and will strengthen its position as a RAN provider on the market

Octavic	OCT will extend their capabilities for the sawmill and wood-construction industries • will integrate their existing platform with the new tools developed in this project and will put the integrated solution on the market.
TalTech	TalTech will potentially commercialise localisation solutions developed; will consult and serve local companies in terms of 5G networks installations, AR and DT use for the industry digitalization: support industrial digitalisation rate to achieve European average; participate R&D and business activities related to buildings renovation in Estonia, Finland, Sweden; target spin-offing IoT-based monitoring solutions for WVC and construction sector with the focus on data analysis. Acquired knowledge and IP supports TalTech ambitions in contributing to Green Transition commercial projects and spin- off creation.

8. Clustering Activities

As part of 5G-TIMBER's effort to enhance our dissemination and communication plan and to maximize the impact of the project, we intend to establish a clustering plan and collaboration system with existing networks and ecosystems (existing partnerships/projects and initiatives, etc.), as well as relevant HEU projects that are related to the 5G-TIMBER objectives and scope. Table 8 presents an early list of existing projects/initiatives related to 5G-TIMBER and potential collaboration opportunities.

Table 8 Related projects/initiatives

Sister Projects	Brief description	Coordinator	5G-TIMBER partners involved
RE4DY (GA 101058384)	data-driven digital value networks 4.0 in manufacturing	INNOVALIA (ES)	Politecnico di Milano
Zero-Swarm (GA 101057083)	aims climate neutral and digitized production via a multidisciplinary, human centric, objective oriented innovative approach resulting in technical solutions for open swarm framework, non-public 5G network, active information continuum and digital twin.	CERTH (GR)	Accelleran
Other Related projects	Brief description	Coordinator	5G-TIMBER partners involved
5G-ROUTES (GA 951867)	5th Generation connected and automated mobility cross-border EU trials	Ericsson (EE)	Inlecom; Taltech
5G-CONNI (GA 861459)	5G CONNI is a joint EU-Taiwan project within the European	Fraunhofer (DE)	Athonet

	Union Horizon 2020 program that brings together major players in ICT and Industry 4.0 from Europe and Taiwan with the joint vision of paving the way for industrial 5G applications and accelerating deployments.		
FUDGE-5G (GA 957242)	FULLY DisinteGrated private nEtworks for 5G verticals	Uni Polit Valencia (ES)	Athonet, Thales FR
BASAJAUN (GA 862942)	Sustainable wood construction for rural development and urban transformation	Tecnalia (ES)	VTT; Innovawood
EcoReFibre (GA 101057473)	develop and demonstrate innovative demos for environmentally sound and commercially viable recycling of end-of-life fibreboards, which currently have no commercially viable recycling methods	Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences (SE)	Innovawood
Other Related projects	Brief description		
Wood4Bauhaus	The European wood-based sector has launched the Wood Sector Alliance for the New European Bauhaus (Wood4Bauhaus) to establish an open platform that brings together its manifold stakeholders.		
5G PPP	The 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G PPP) is a joint initiative between the European Commission and the European ICT industry.		
Made in Europe Partnership	Voice and driver for sustainable manufacturing in Europe based on joined expertise and resources. It will boost European manufacturing ecosystems towards global leadership in technology, towards circular industries and flexibility.		
6G-IA	The 6G Smart Networks and Services Industry Association (6G-IA) is the voice of European Industry and Research for next generation networks and services. Its primary objective is to contribute to Europe's leadership on 5G, 5G evolution and SNS/6G research.		

CHX, in collaboration with the project coordinator, will engage with the sister projects coordinators and invite them for a network meeting. Following the meeting, the 3 projects will develop a Joint Clustering Board and Plan that will include the following activities:

- creation of a common identity (logo),
- mailing list,
- promotion of sister projects on 5G-TIMBER website,
- yearly meetings,
- invitation to 5G-TIMBER events.

The other projects and initiatives identified and other relevant ones will be approached by CHX in order to establish synergies and support towards relevant activities.

9. Management and monitoring of activities

9.1. Partner's Responsibilities

All partners are involved in communication and dissemination activities to various extents, as stated in the Grant Agreement. While task leaders, work package leaders, and the coordinator are expected to be heavily involved, it is crucial that technical participants and use case hosts provide their input as well by reaching out to CHX (5gtimber@crowdhelix.com) and corresponding WP leader.

To facilitate internal communication within the consortium, a [MS 365 Teams area](#) has been generated as a repository for important files. The Teams folders will be used as storage areas for important legal documents, information from meetings including minutes, Gantt chart, profiling material, deliverables submitted, data, as well as a day-to-day working area for the implementation of tasks and the project in general. Teams also includes a [Template folder](#) which should be used for either internal or external communications. All information circulated will be treated as consortium confidential unless stated otherwise.

A [dissemination tracker spreadsheet](#) has been created in order to keep track of the consortium's dissemination activities. The consortium partners are required to report in this spreadsheet the activities conducted in the framework of communication and dissemination of 5G-TIMBER. The file includes three tabs:

- Communication activities: contains information related to communication activities conducted by the consortium partners.

9.2. Monitoring

The Grant Agreement (GA) sets Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), seen below in table 9, that will help us to monitor the dissemination and communication status and activities of the project.

Table 9 Communication and dissemination KPIs

Activity	Expected Results
5G-TIMBER Website	Unique visitors M12: 1000; M36: 2000 Public deliverables: > 20
Social Media	LinkedIn, Twitter, Facebook followers: >200 each; LinkedIn & Twitter: 200 retweets, Facebook likes: >1000; Banners: >30
Scientific Publications	Journals/magazines >9 ; Conferences >20; demonstrations: >6
Videos	2 online video clips: 2 with > 1000 views;
Communication/ Dissemination materials	Project flyers: >3; Posters & roll-up banners: >3; press releases: >5; Newsletters: >6; Technical factsheets: 3; Non-technical factsheets: 3
Events/Conferences	Industrial exhibitions: >9; booths >3 Training: online tutorials: 3; Number of hackathons: 2
Outreach	Made in Europe and 5G-PPP: WGs to contribute: 7; Interactions with fora/initiatives: >4
Timber Helix	>150 stakeholders engaged by the end of the project.

These KPIs represent a concrete way of measuring tangible results, and the communication and dissemination plan will be periodically reviewed to ensure they are reached. By constantly comparing the results of the evaluation with the set targets, CHX will be able to establish which areas need to be improved, adapting future actions accordingly.

10. Conclusion

The 5G-TIMBER Dissemination, Communication and Clustering Plan presented in this document aims to outline the project's audiences, key messages, communication channels, roles and responsibilities and methods of communication to be used by answering the questions (WHO? WHAT? WHEN? HOW?).

A wide and sustained effort across the project lifetime will be required to maximise the awareness and increase the impact of the project, its activities and the expected results. This document will help consortium members sustain these efforts as the project progresses.

The proposed activities, tools, and channels are calculated to reach the broadest audience possible. However, to ensure the quality of the communication and dissemination activities, KPIs and evaluation times were defined.

This document will be reviewed and updated during the project lifespan in order to adapt to the project implementation status and current information. These updates will be directly reported in D6.2 (M18) and D6.3 (M36), as well as in D7.10 (M9).

Some of the central steps until the technical review (D7.10 (M9)) and D6.2 (M18) include:

- Monitoring and ensuring that all partners actively engage in their planned DCCP activities;
- Manage (CHX) and lead (Innovawood) the build-up and uptake of the 5G-TIMBER Helix;

- Liaise with EFFRA (Made in Europe Partnership) to understand their expectations towards the 5G-TIMBER project and update this DCCP accordingly;
- Develop a clustering plan with the sister projects: Zero-Swarm and Re4dy;
- Animate 5G-Timber's communication channels (website and social media);
- Create and update communication materials (posters, roll-up, brochure, newsletter).

11. Appendix 1

THE CONTEXT

It is expected that in the coming years, the implementation of 5G in the EU manufacturing sector will drive €458.3 billion in additional industry revenues and €131.8 billion in added GDP contributions. The use of 5G technology along with other enabling technologies, such as edge-computing and AI, can bring up to 20% to 30% increase in productivity. However, 5G and smart manufacturing are currently more widely adopted in verticals with high-volume, easily standardisable, low-margin business models where cost-savings and productivity efficiency are necessary to achieving economies of scale. The use of 5G, edge-computing AI by small and medium manufacturers is rare due to costly technological risks and lack of best practices.

CONTACT

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Do you want to know more about 5G-TIMBER?
www.5g-timber.eu

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TWIN TRANSITION FOR THE TIMBER INDUSTRY

www.5g-timber.eu

OUR OBJECTIVE

Support the rapid uptake of 5G technologies, considering real industrial practices and constraints in the EU timber industry over the whole value chain, focusing on small-volume manufacturing industries.

Working closely with wood industries, 5G-Timber aims to increase wood-based materials recycling by 50%, increase productivity by 15%, reach 99% of the work done in the factory (vs. 85% today), reduce on-site work by 10%, reduce product non-conformities by 10%, and increase workers' safety in wooden houses production and onsite assembling.

WHAT WE WANT TO ACHIEVE

1. Accelerate the **twin green and digital transition** of the manufacturing and construction sectors.
2. Create **green, flexible and digital ways to build and produce goods**.
3. Increase the **attractiveness and safety** in manufacturing and construction jobs and point the way to opportunities that allow workers to upskill.
4. Set out a **credible pathway to contributing to climate neutral, circular, and digitalised energy intensive industries**.
5. Increase **productivity, innovation capacity, resilience, sustainability and global competitiveness** of European energy intensive industries.
6. Contribute to a **substantial reduction of waste and CO2 emissions**.

THE CONSORTIUM

The 5G-TIMBER consortium consists of 16 organisations from 10 countries.

Figure 6 5G-Timber brochure